

Preliminary Studies on Seed-Polysaccharides of *Phaseolus vulgaris* and *Phaseolus aureus*

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Phaseolus vulgaris and *Phaseolus aureus* belong to the same family Leguminaceae and although these species do not differ in their chromosome number, the seeds have different morphological appearance. Since polysaccharides are important constituents of the seeds, systematic investigations on the nature of the polysaccharides were considered essential and interesting.

Paper chromatography was carried out by descending method using Whatman No. 1 filter paper for qualitative and quantitative separation of sugars. The solvent systems were (1) ethyl acetate : pyridine : water (8 : 2 : 1), (2) ethyl acetate : pyridine : acetic acid : water (5 : 5 : 1 : 3) and (3) *n*-butyl alcohol : ethanol : water (4 : 1 : 5) upper layer. Reducing sugars were located on chromatograms by spraying with (1) alkaline silver nitrate and (2) aqueous saturated aniline oxalate. All evaporations were carried out at 35°–40° *in vacuo*.

Isolation of the polysaccharides from Phaseolus vulgaris : The outer skin of the seeds were removed and the seeds were macerated in a high speed 'Kenmix-55' blender for ten minutes in presence of ethanol. The pulp was kept under ethanol for 2hr, squeezed through a nylon cloth and was dried in air. The powder was kept with a mixture of benzene and ethanol (2 : 1) in a water bath (60°–70°) for half an hour while shaking and filtered. This process was repeated five times and finally the material was dried in air.

Cold water extraction : The powder (17 g.) was stirred with water (200 ml.) at room temperature for 4hr. and the slurry was filtered through a nylon cloth. The solution was clarified in a high speed centrifuge, ethanol was added to precipitate the polysaccharide V_1 which was removed at the centrifuge, washed and triturated repeatedly with absolute alcohol and ether. Yield of the air-dried material, 0.32 g. To the supernatant sufficient lithium chloride was added to make it 1% with respect to the salt and excess ethanol containing 1% LiCl was added to give a second fraction (V_2). Yield, 0.07 g.

Hot water extraction : The material remaining after the above extraction was stirred with water (200 ml) at boiling waterbath temperature for 4 hr. The extract was clarified and the polysaccharides V_3 and V_4 were isolated as in the case of cold water extract. Yield, 0.36 g. and 0.03 g. respectively.

Extraction with sodium hydroxide solution : The residue left after hot water extraction, was stirred with 0.1N sodium hydroxide solution (200 ml) in presence of nitrogen. The extract was removed, clarified and the pH was adjusted to 4.5 with acetic acid when a polysaccharide

(V₅) precipitated out. After separation of V₅, polysaccharide V₆ was isolated by adding ethanol (400 ml). Yield : V₅, 0.51 g.; V₆, 0.16 g. The residue was finally treated with 1.0N sodium hydroxide solution and polysaccharides V₇ and V₈ were isolated as in the case of 0.1N sodium hydroxide extract. Yield : V₇, 0.85 g.; V₈, 3.5 g. All the polysaccharides were washed, triturated and dried as described earlier.

TABLE 1

Properties and composition of the polysaccharide fractions obtained from Phaseolus vulgaris and Phaseolus aureus.

Polysaccharide	Ash %	Moisture %	Sugar components and their ratio				
V ₁	nil	7.4	Ga :	Ar			
			1.4	1.0			
V ₂	nil	8.4	Ga :	Ar			
			1.5	1.0			
V ₃	0.20	6.1	Ga :	Glu :	Ar :	Xy	
			1.0	8.7	1.0	0.2	
V ₄	0.15	6.6	Ga :	Glu :	Ar :	Xy	
			0.5	4.8	1.0	0.3	
V ₅	0.30	10.2	Ga :	Glu :	Mann :	Ar :	Xy
			0.4	0.6	0.1	1.0	0.1
V ₆	0.40	9.7	Ga :	Glu :	Mann :	Ar :	Xy
			0.6	2.6	0.2	1.0	0.2
V ₇	0.50	8.5	Ga :	Glu :	Mann :	Ar :	Xy
			0.4	19.2	1.0	1.0	0.4
V ₈	0.40	8.1	Ga :	Glu :	Mann :	Ar :	Xy
			0.4	26.8	0.4	1.0	0.4
A ₁	nil	5.5	Ga :	Glu :	Mann :	Ar	
			1.3	3.2	0.3	1.0	
A ₂	nil	7.1	Ga :	Glu :	Ar		
			0.6	1.4	1.0		
A ₃	nil	9.2	Ga :	Glu :	Mann :	Ar	
			0.8	14.3	1.0	1.0	
A ₄	0.15	6.6	Glu :	Mann :	Ar		
			12.0	1.9	1.0		
A ₅	0.25	8.3	Glu :	Ar			
			4.8	1.0			
A ₆	0.30	9.5	Glu :	Ar			
			27.0	1.0			
A ₇	0.25	6.8	Ga :	Glu :	Ar :	Xy	
			0.2	20.8	1.0	0.2	
A ₈	0.20	8.4	Ga :	Glu :	Ar :	Xy	
			0.2	1.3	1.0	0.4	

Ga = galactose, Glu = glucose, Mann = mannose, Ar = arabinose, Xy = xylose.

Isolation of the polysaccharides from seeds of Phaseolus aureus : The seeds were freed from outer skins, macerated, defatted and the powdered material was obtained as in the case of earlier seed. This (18 g.) was extracted successively with (1) cold water, (2) hot water, (3) 0.1*N* sodium hydroxide solution and (4) 1.0*N* sodium hydroxide solution and the extracts were filtered through nylon cloth and then clarified in a high speed centrifuge. Eight fractions designated as polysaccharides A₁, A₂, A₃, A₄, A₅, A₆, A₇ and A₈ were isolated under conditions identical to those used in the case of *Phaseolus vulgaris*. Yield A₁ 0.30 g.; A₂ 0.08 g.; A₃ 3.01g.; A₄ 0.17 g.; A₅ 0.19 g.; A₆ 0.08 g.; A₇ 0.14 g.; and A₈ 0.37 g.

Identification of the sugar components : The polysaccharide (20 mg.) was hydrolysed¹ by heating with 2*N* sulphuric acid (2 ml.) on a boiling water bath for 16 hr. The solution was neutralised with barium carbonate, filtered and the neutral solution was concentrated to a syrup (2 ml.). Paper chromatographic examination of the syrup in three different solvent systems was carried out and the monosaccharide components of each fraction were given in Table 1.

Quantitative estimation of sugars : The polysaccharide (80 mg.) was hydrolysed with 2*N* sulphuric acid in a sealed tube. Ribose (40 mg.) was mixed with the hydrolyzate as reference sugar, neutralised (BaCO₃), filtered, concentrated and the solution was made upto a known volume (2.0 ml.). 0.20 ml. of the mixture was separated by quantitative paper chromatography into its constituent sugars and the zones corresponding to each sugar were identified with guide spots. These were cut, eluted with water (5.0 ml.) and the amount of each monosaccharide was determined by periodate method². Table 1 shows the ratio of the amounts of different sugars in each fraction.

Percentage contents of ash and moisture of each fraction were determined and recorded in Table 1. Investigations on the isolation and characterization of different homogenous polysaccharides are under progress.

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1. Baker and Hulton, *Biochem. J.*, 1920, **14**, 754.
2. E. L. Hirst and J. K. N. Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1659.